

CAREER SELECTION MOTIVATIONS FOR WOMEN POLICE OFFICERS AND ACTIVITIES FOR INSPIRING GIRL STUDENTS IN SCHOOLS

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INTRODUCTION

The work contributed by women is a significant factor in a nation's progress. It is said, without women participating in the national activities, the overall social, economic and political achievements of a country will come to a standstill. The patriarchal notions of the Indian society, believing that man is the primary in the family, is changing in the contemporary world.

One of the most important factors that lead people to their goals is the drive. This drive is known as motivation. For every individual there is a variable driving force. In fact, it is not just a single factor, but a combination of factors that lead people to achieve their goals.

Focus on an external goal, such as financial success, is known as "extrinsic" motivation, while enjoyment is known as "intrinsic" motivation. Both are very important for career success but in different ways. [Extrinsic](#) motivation leads to better performance, while [intrinsic](#) motivation to a deeper, more thorough way of learning.(Skatova 2014)

Types of Motivation

It is true, in India, women today receive the same education as men, and nearly all prepare for some occupation. Ironically, very few of them are promoted to pursue employment in public world.

It is easy to see that achievement motivation, or lack of it, in females is a consequence of several factors working together. The factors that impinge upon women's achievement, their academic productivity, career growth and their familial responsibility vary greatly in terms of rank, class, region, profession, type of family and decision making ability of the women careerist concerned. Women do not constitute a homogenous category and therefore, their problems appear multifarious

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several prior studies have found that career choices are determined by many, sometimes quite different motives.

In this context, some theories for understanding the reasons underlying the decision to begin a specific occupational or entrepreneurial career have been developed over time. As a result, the Theory of Social Learning (Bandura, 1977), the Entrepreneurial Event Theory (Shapero & Sokol, 1982) and the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) have emerged as the most promising approaches. The central element of these theories is the individual's intention to undertake and to put a specific behaviour into practice, influenced by motivational elements. In general, the motives can be classified into cognitive personal factors on the one hand; contextual or environmental factors on the other. They can exert positive or negative influence on the intended career, and often their specific combination and interaction moulds the individual's decision to enter a particular career path.

Research studying the reasons women are under-represented in policing has generally focused on four areas of the employment process: attracting women to the field, recruiting women to apply, hiring and testing procedures, and retaining women over careers. (Meagher & Yentes, 1986; Raganella & White, 2004; White, Cooper, Saunders, & Raganella, 2010).

The most relevant influence seems to be the perceived social pressure from family, friends or significant other 'people of reference' (Ajzen, 1991). Previous studies have shown that role models influence career choice; they particularly appear to encourage entrepreneurial careers (Krueger Jr., Reilly, & Carsrud, 2000). Several scholars have shown the influence of parents' professional activities on children's career decisions, as they often prefer to work in the same field as their parents (Duchesneau & Gartner, 1990; Scherer,

While a substantial amount of research has examined the motivation for individuals to become police officers, very little is known about why Chinese citizens choose this profession. Using survey data collected from cadets in a Chinese police college, this study attempts to answer three questions: (1) who are the people that decide to become police cadets in China; (2) what are the factors that motivate cadets to choose the police profession, and (3) how do personal characteristics influence cadets' motivations to join the force? The results indicate that Chinese cadets in the sample are largely single, young males from middle-class families. They tended to have some college education while their parents were likely to have attained a lower educational level. Job security and benefits, the opportunity to help people, the desire to enforce the law, and parental influences were important factors that motivated police cadets at this institution to join the force.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Career Selection Motivations

It implies a desire with respect to choosing an occupation. A multidimensional construct that combines elements of needs, interests, and personality characteristics that reflect the stimulus, direction, and persistence of job-related behaviours.

Women police officers

A woman who is a member of the Indian or state police force of rank Police Sub Inspector (PSI) or above.

Activities for inspiring girl students in schools

Curricular activities planned and executed in the schools to inspire the girl students to take up jobs-with-uniforms like police officers, piolets and armed forces (Jobs-with-uniform).

RESEARCH QUESTIONS.

1. What motivates women officers to join the police force?
2. How schools can motivate girl students to select jobs-with-uniform?

OBJECTIVES

1. To understand the motivations that led women officers to join police force in India.
2. To know the curricular activities to be planned and executed in the school to motivate girl students to take up jobs-with uniform.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study focuses the collection and analysis of qualitative data from both primary and secondary sources.

Primary data is collected through an interview of a women police officer working in Mumbai Police Force through the open-ended response questions in a semi-structured interview to know the curricular activities to be planned and executed in the school to motivate girl students to take up jobs-with uniform.

The secondary data is collected from the interviews; You tube videos, websites and research papers to understand the motivations that led women officers to join police force in India.

DATA ANALYSIS

The analysis includes data reduction, transcription of interviews, and conclusion drawing.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Ms. Sadguna is a retired sub inspector in Mahila police thana and is 34 years of age when she was looking for a job she came across an advertisement and took a decision and join the police force.

Ms. Badola is retired station incharge of the Mahila police thana of Kanpur police her husband is a police personnel and he encouraged her to study and apply for the job.

Ms. Ambika is retired as Deputy Superintendent of Police (DSP) in Mumbai. Got inspired to join police force after her marriage when she attended a Police officer's event.

Ms. Meera Borwankar is retired first woman Police Commissioner of Mumbai. Joined police force taking inspiration from Ms. Kiran Bedi and her teacher.

Ms. Kiran Bedi is retired first female Indian Police Service Officer. Interaction with senior civil servants in Amritsar motivated her to take up a public service career.

Ms. Manisha Shirke is working as PSI in Mumbai. Joined police force because of her mother.

The findings can be summarised as follows:

- Women officers joined the police force before marriage as well as after marriage.
- Persons working on higher posts inspired two women.
- Family support helped two officers take up the police officers job.
- One officer was fascinated by the uniform hence became a police officer.
- One officer joined the police force when she came across an advertisement in the newspaper.

Activities that can be undertaken in the schools to encourage girl students:

- Inviting officers from different government departments for various programmes.
- Arranging visits to various government offices like police stations, naval offices, fire stations etc.
- Including inspiring stories of women achievers in school curriculum.
- Inviting eminent parents as guest lecturers,
- Providing and reading Newspapers, Employment news etc. in the schools.

CONCLUSION

Women empowerment needs multifarious efforts. Schools should take up the responsibility for providing inspiring experiences to the girl students and so does the government agencies. Curriculum and learning experiences should be planned to motivate girls to take up challenging careers in future. Teachers should ensure motivation of girl students in the classroom transactions.

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